

EFFICIENCY OF INTERNET TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Advantages, disadvantages and ways of implementing Internet technologies in teaching foreign languages are considered in this article. The author points out that the World Web gives students an opportunity of cross-cultural communication that leads to overriding the existing stereotypes and developing socio-cultural tolerance in students. Moreover, the article discusses the role of Internet technologies in developing students' speech skills and professionally relevant competences.

Keywords: information technologies, multimedia technologies, virtual language environment, Internet addiction, distance learning.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern postindustrial society, multimedia technologies are considered to be the most promising and popular pedagogical technologies in the field of teaching foreign languages. And Internet is the most developed and accessible multimedia environment for users. The mediatized virtual environment allows for synchronous and asynchronous learning of students, providing tools for creating and delivering courses, lessons, materials (including examinations), for tracking grades and providing feedback to both individual students and groups [1, p. 290-291].

The global spread of the English language, the active involvement of practicing teachers and authors of textbooks in the process of mastering the Internet space led to the creation of resource bases - Internet sites that provide teachers with the latest materials as in text and illustrative format, so and in the format of multimedia programs for those who teach and study foreign languages. Many teachers use Internet sites and resources such as dictionaries, encyclopedias and other materials. Moreover, teachers can not only use existing training sites, but also create their own, where students can receive current information adapted to the needs of a specific audience.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A large number of authentic, timely updated materials allow students to be in a virtual language environment, read, see and hear samples of modern foreign language

speech and use them to generate their own statements. Thus, the use of the Internet contributes to the development of students' basic speech skills such:

- ✓ writing (email and blogs correspondence);
- ✓ reading (familiarity with the content text sites, reading messages in email and blogs);
- ✓ listening (listening and watching audio /video materials, listening to the interlocutor's speech through application Skype);
- ✓ speaking (communication through software such as Skype, IMO, ZOOM)

Computers can also help ELL students develop their writing skills as well. According to Lewis, the composition for beginning learners should be a guided activity so students do not become bored. Writing paragraphs in a language that is still somewhat unfamiliar to students can be difficult. When using a computer, however, the use of graphics can make this much more enjoyable. [1, p. 14]

There are still no unambiguous opinions on how effective is the use of Internet resources directly in the audience. After all, this is associated with both certain methodological advantages and organizational risks. Benefits include the ability to demonstrate a particular phenomenon, including linguistic, view the latest press, news videos, illustrate material, given in the tutorial. These form of activities are effective for seniors undergraduate and graduate students. However, there are often cases when, when trying to listen to (video) the news program in real time, the teacher is faced with a lack of understanding by the audience of audio / video text, which cannot be repeated if you do not perform parallel recording of news blog. This negates the effect from listening or watching material. It therefore means that the preparation classes with the presentation of materials from the Internet requires the teacher to preliminary methodical processing. With regard to the use of Internet materials for junior students, it is highly recommended to collect, organize and process them, turning them into secondary texts corresponding to the language the level of students. However, excessive enthusiasm for Internet resources can have a negative impact on both students and the educational process, moreover, lead to the development of Internet addiction and to desocialization of personality. Internet technologies offer ample opportunities for international and intercultural communication. These include e-mail, blogging, Internet conferencing, and teleconferencing. Communication with peers in a foreign language helps students better understand mindset of another culture representatives and overcome existing sociocultural stereotypes. This, in turn, contributes not only to the formation of sociocultural competence, but also to the development sociocultural tolerance of students. Virtual communication is one of the types of communication, therefore it can be considered in all its multi-functionality as a complex of speech and nonspeech

manifestations of subjects. P.N. Ermakov and V.A. Labunsky are distinguished by the following communication functions: information communicative, regulatory communicative and affectively communicative [2, p. 301]. As with direct communication, communicative, cognitive, role relationships can arise in a virtual environment. However, the virtual space allows you to change the usual model of relations with others, to "try on" a new social role - especially in distance learning in the format of a role-playing game, - to show their knowledge, which a student usually cannot demonstrate due to isolation, shyness, or the presence of a stable behavioral stereotype [3, p. 26].

Internet technologies have made a great contribution to the development of distance education, which in the last decade has managed to gain popularity in all over the world. The spread of this form of education has given rise to the belief among some users that a foreign language can be learned through the Internet, not leaving your home or office. This rather dangerous misconception is shared by numerous creators of multimedia programs and video courses. In recent years, their products have been actively offered by various training centers. Most of these programs are addressed to foreign language learners or "false beginners". Some courses involve the independent study of a foreign language; others suggest doing this on the basis of educational methodological centers with the participation of a teacher. It should be reminded that it is precisely such a form of foreign language learning was offered to a wide audience in the 1970s and 1980s. via television programs "I am learning English", "English for children", as well as via the use of the few video courses of foreign languages such as "Muzzy in Gondoland" at that time. Difference in the fact that today a multimedia course of a foreign language is posted on the Internet or recorded on a CDD disc, and the role of the announcer - the host of the TV program is performed by a sound and animated computer program. On the one hand, there is progress in the use of computer multimedia technologies, but, on the other hand, as before, students do not have the opportunity to communicate with the teacher, to find out what mistakes they have made, i.e. there is no feedback during training, and language learning comes down to self-education. The use of distance learning can be effective only when the student can study the subject on his own and test himself using control questions with keys; In this case while the learning process takes place on a language that the student is fluent in and has no difficulty in choosing forms of expression. Learning a foreign language involves not just memorizing lexical grammatical units, making sentences and translating texts, as it is proposed to do in many modern multimedia programs, but the formation of skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing. It is impossible to accomplish this task without the supervision of the teacher, since each person is a linguistic personality formed on the basis of their native language and

culture. Therefore, each student will make his own, individual mistakes that require correction. It cannot be denied that some mistakes are common and students can be helped to avoid them by doing specific exercises. However, it is impossible to predict what phonetic, lexical, grammatical, stylistic or semantic error a student will make. Therefore, participation of a teacher is vital any form of distance learning of a foreign language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

One of the founders of the Russian distance education schools E.S. Polat emphasized that the materials offered in distance learning courses are electronic textbooks of a modular nature, with their own specifics, therefore, they should be developed not only by teachers and programmers, enthusiasts, but by scientific methodologists who own telecommunications technologies [4]. Modern multimedia technologies make it possible to provide the user with text and audio material with the apparatus of exercises, which the teacher of the training center checks and sends to the student by e-mail. Some success in developing reading, listening, translating and writing skills can be achieved by offering highly structured and algorithmic exercises systems which a computer program can test:

- choosing the correct word (answer, grammatical form) out of several sentences;
- substitution of words from the proposed list in gaps in the text (sentence);
- substitution of words from the listened (viewed excerpt) in gaps in text (sentence);
- making sentences from given words or word combinations;
- composing a letter (or other letter document) according to the proposed model;

Assignments can also be reviewed by the instructor by e-mailing them and then sending them back to the student with an appropriate comment. The development of the skill of oral speech involves not only the development of speech models in exercises (including in the presence of audio text or video), but also the generation of one's own statements addressed to the interlocutor. To do this, you can organize video consultations using a webcam or use telephone communication and the Skype and ZOOM programs. However, the use of the above multimedia can be challenging due to the lack of students of the necessary material base, which in many cases is due to the high cost of equipment. Generally effective distance learning speaking in a foreign language is often geographic remoteness impedes student from teacher, difference in time zones, mismatch in the personal schedule of teacher and student. Nevertheless, distance learning can be successfully used to prepare for exams or other tests, in preparatory courses, in the system of secondary and additional education. One of the conditions for successful learning is not just the motivation of students, but their

readiness for systematic independent work. Internet technologies are becoming universal: training courses designed to automate and intensify traditional learning are easily and quickly transferred to the Internet, and vice versa, a course written for the Internet can be used autonomously for traditional learning using new information technologies. According to O.A.Vdovina, the Internet stimulates curiosity, unregulated and multivariate learning, develops no stereotypical thinking, “which is characterized by the ability to put forward many correct ideas, speed, flexibility, originality, accuracy” [5, p. 53]. Using clip art can also help students to convey their thoughts more clearly. The advantages provided by the Internet in organization of cooperation are predestined by the very nature of the Network. As it is known, the World Wide Web (WWW) was formed as an environment specifically designed for collaborative work on the documents by collectives of researchers territorially remote from each other. “The further development of Internet technologies has given an opportunity for joint use and editing of textual materials, schedules, audio and video sequences.” According to P. Groves, with the co-authors, the pedagogical significance of the given type of Internet technologies consists in the fact that it allows the trainee not only to be involved in the single context of teaching, but also creates opportunities for interaction with others and with the teacher. In this respect it differs sharply from such types of educational activity as, for example, obtaining data from the web (web browsing). [2, p.55]

CONCLUSION

Psychological and pedagogical studies of the effectiveness of the use of Internet technologies allow us to come to the following conclusions:

— Internet technologies allow teachers of foreign languages to effectively use the educational resources of the World Wide Web and promptly update language material.

— The use of Internet technologies contributes to the development of basic speech skills and professionally significant competencies of students.

— Internet technologies allow for intercultural communication, and this, in turn, contributes to the understanding of a different linguistic culture and the development of socio-cultural tolerance of students.

— The use of Internet technologies develops students’ curiosity, non-stereotypical thinking, flexibility. At the same time, an excessive interest in the Internet can lead to the development of Internet addiction and changes in the student’s personality.

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